

The Connection Between Attacks On Health Facilities in Gaza and Article 599 of Indonesia's 2023 Criminal Code: Indonesia's Role Through the Principle of Universality

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ABSTRACT: The ongoing conflict between Palestine and Israel has led to a severe humanitarian crisis, including repeated military attacks on healthcare facilities. A concrete example is the series of attacks targeting the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza, which escalated from arson, artillery shelling, and forced evacuation to its seizure as a military base by Israeli forces between October 2023 and April 2026. This study analyzes the connection between the attacks on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza and the provisions of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code regarding crimes against humanity, as well as examines Indonesia's role through the principle of universality under Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code. This study employs a normative legal approach by examining the 2023 Criminal Code, the 1998 Rome Statute, and Additional Protocol I to the 1977 Geneva Conventions. The results of the discussion indicate that the repeated attacks on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza meet the indicators of widespread and systematic attacks against the civilian population, and have resulted in casualties and forced displacement, consistent with the provisions of Article 599(a) of the 2023 Criminal Code. Furthermore, Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code provides a strong normative basis for Indonesia to apply the principle of universality, which allows the state to prosecute perpetrators of international crimes committed outside its jurisdiction without being bound by nationality. Thus, this study affirms that the 2023 Criminal Code can serve as a relevant national legal instrument to support the protection of human rights and the enforcement of international law.

KEYWORDS: Indonesian Hospital in Gaza, Crimes Against Humanity, Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code, Principle of Universality.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Palestinian-Israeli conflict began with the arrival of the Israeli people (Jews) in the Palestinian territories, where they failed to treat the Arab people (Palestinians) as the rightful owners of the land. Subsequently, the adoption of UN Resolution 181 in 1947, which partitioned Palestine into two states, an Arab state (Palestine) and a Jewish state (Israel), exacerbated the conflict between the two nations. This resolution served as the basis for David Ben-Gurion, who at the time was the head of the Jewish Agency, to declare the establishment of Israel on May 14, 1948. The declaration was rejected by the Arab community, leading to the outbreak of the 1948 Arab-Israeli War the very next day, in which Arab states (Lebanon, Jordan, Egypt, Iraq, Saudi Arabia, and Syria), alongside Palestinian militias, attacked Israel (Firdaus & Yani, 2020).

In the process, the Palestinian-Israeli issue escalated into a conflict between Hamas (an Islamic resistance movement) and Israel. On October 7, 2023, Hamas attacked the Nova music festival north of Re'im Kibbutz, about 6 km east of Gaza. The attack involved surrounding and firing upon festival attendees, who were civilians. As a result, more than 260 people were killed at the scene, and a number of people were also taken hostage by Hamas. Following Hamas's attack on October 7, 2023, Israel launched a retaliatory rocket strike targeting Hamas. However, the strike also hit various civilian structures such as schools, hospitals, and public facilities. Subsequently, in November 2023, Israel attacked the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza, causing damage to several of the hospital's facilities (Sean Seddon, 2023).

According to a statement from a spokesperson for the Israeli armed forces, the attack was carried out on the grounds that Hamas had built military facilities beneath the hospital as a shelter in case of Israeli airstrikes. However, this claim was refuted by the presidium of the Medical Emergency Rescue Committee (MER-C), the coordinator of the Indonesian Hospital Development Program, thereby raising doubts. Under Article 52(3) of Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions, civilian objects must not be targeted and must continue to be treated as civilian objects even if their status is unclear (Luc, 2023).

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Israel's attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza constitutes a violation of Article 8(2)(b)(xxiv) of the 1998 Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, which states: "Intentionally directing attacks against buildings, material, medical units and transport, and personnel using the distinctive emblems of the Geneva Conventions in conformity with international law." Based on this provision, Israel's actions can be classified as war crimes for attacking the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza. Furthermore, Israel's actions also violate Additional Protocol I to the 1977 Geneva Conventions. Specifically, Article 12, which emphasizes the protection of medical units, and Article 52, paragraphs (1) and (2), which prohibit targeting civilian objects as the object of attacks or reprisals (Arlina Permanasari, 1999).

According to Wanda Hamidah, in a webinar organized by the Indonesian School of Law (STHI) Jentera titled "The Application of the Principle of Universal Jurisdiction in the New Criminal Code Regarding Crimes Against Humanity and Genocide in Palestine," the Israeli military has carried out 41 attacks on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza, with an additional 13 cases of forced displacement and 4 armed attacks between October 7, 2023, and July 2025. These repeated attacks constitute a threat to hospitals as critical civilian infrastructure and represent a grave violation of human rights (Fachri, 2026).

This is supported by a report from Kompas.com stating that the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza is now being used as a headquarters by the Israeli military, following repeated attacks and damage. Israel has also hung a propaganda banner reading "Rising Lion" with the Israeli flag symbol atop the hospital building, which has been damaged by the conflict. The action reportedly took place in early April 2026 and was accompanied by activities deemed provocative. The Medical Emergency Rescue Committee (MER-C) asserts that the occupation of northern Gaza and the use of civilian facilities, including hospitals, constitute a violation of humanitarian law (Pristiandaru, 2026).

In the context of the 2023 Criminal Code, Article 599 specifically criminalizes acts classified as "crimes against humanity" when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against the civilian population, including acts such as murder, forcible displacement, deprivation of liberty, torture, inhuman acts, discriminatory persecution, as well as sexual violence and forms of enforced disappearance. The presence of Article 599 provides a normative basis in Indonesian national law to assess and, if the elements are met, prosecute acts falling within the scope of crimes against humanity resulting from the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza.

In addition, the provisions on the principle of universality in the 2023 Criminal Code (Articles 6 and 7) allow for the application of Indonesian criminal law to perpetrators of international crimes committed outside the country's territory or for prosecutions assumed by Indonesia under international agreements. These provisions create a legal framework for Indonesia to play a role in holding accountable those responsible for serious violations involving any person (whether an Indonesian citizen or a foreign national) who commits acts considered inherently evil (*super mala per se*) and that are widely condemned by society (strong public condemnation).

Given this background, the issues to be discussed in this study are:

1. What is the connection between the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza and the provisions of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code, which addresses crimes against humanity?
2. What role can Indonesia play in invoking the universal principles guaranteed under Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code to seek legal accountability for Israel's attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza?

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study employs a normative legal research methodology (doctrinal legal research) using legislative, conceptual, and case-based approaches. The legislative approach is used to analyze the provisions of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code, as well as Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code, which pertain to the principle of universality. The conceptual approach is used to examine the concepts of war crimes, crimes against humanity, and the principle of universality in international criminal law. Meanwhile, the case-based approach is used to examine the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza as the subject of legal analysis. The types of legal materials used in this study consist of primary, secondary, and tertiary legal materials. Primary legal materials include the 2023 Criminal Code, the 1998 Rome Statute, and Additional Protocol I to the 1977 Geneva Conventions. Secondary legal materials consist of books, academic journals, articles, news reports, and expert opinions related to crimes against humanity and international humanitarian law. Tertiary legal materials are used to aid in the explanation of legal terms and to strengthen understanding of the research topic. Data collection was conducted through a literature review by examining various legal documents and literature related to the subject matter. The collected data was then qualitatively analyzed using a descriptive-analytical method. The analysis involved outlining applicable legal provisions, comparing them with the facts of the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza, and drawing conclusions regarding the connection between the incident and Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code, as well as the potential application of the principle of universality by Indonesia. The results of the analysis are presented systematically to address two research questions: the connection between the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza and crimes against humanity, and Indonesia's role in enforcing legal accountability through the principle of universal jurisdiction. Thus, this study aims to produce a comprehensive normative understanding of the legal issues under examination.

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III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Connection Between the Attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza and the Wording of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code Governing Crimes Against Humanity

War crimes are crimes arising from armed conflict, whether international or non-international, that involve grave violations of human rights as guaranteed by International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and other customary rules of war. Article 6 of the Charter of the International Military Tribunal establishes three categories of crimes: crimes against peace, war crimes, and crimes against humanity (Muharrom & Adiwijaya, 2025). There are several key principles in International Humanitarian Law, including (Astuti, 2024):

- a) The Principle of Humanity, which prohibits the use of methods of warfare that are unnecessary to achieve a military advantage;
- b) The Principle of Necessity, allows civilian objects to be targeted by military forces only if they meet certain conditions in accordance with the provisions of international humanitarian law;
- c) The Principle of Proportionality, demand that attacks take into account the potential for civilian casualties so that they do not outweigh the military benefits gained;
- d) The Principle of Distinction, which requires combatants to distinguish themselves from civilians, who must not be attacked or involved in the war;
- e) Prohibition of Causing Unnecessary Suffering, limiting the use of methods and means of warfare so as not to cause undue suffering;
- f) The distinction between Ius Ad Bellum and Ius In Bello, to ensure that the suffering caused by the war is minimized and that the victims receive maximum assistance;
- g) The minimum standards of international humanitarian law, as set forth in Article 3 of the 1949 Geneva Conventions, establish the basic rules for all armed conflicts; and
- h) The principle of responsibility in the implementation and enforcement of international humanitarian law requires states to disseminate international humanitarian law and impose legal sanctions for violations thereof.

In the context of International Humanitarian Law, direct attacks on hospitals, medical centers, and healthcare personnel who are not participating in hostilities constitute grave breaches, as they violate the principles of distinction, proportionality, and humanity. Furthermore, Article 12(1) of Additional Protocol I to the 1977 Geneva Conventions states: “medical units shall be respected and protected at all times and shall not be the object of attack,” as well as Article 52(1), which states, “civilian objects shall not be the object of attack or of reprisals,” followed by the provision in paragraph (2): “attacks shall be limited strictly to military objectives.” This confirms that the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza violated these provisions because it failed to provide protection for medical units and targeted civilian objects.

Article 13(1) of Additional Protocol I to the 1977 Geneva Conventions stipulates that humanitarian legal protection for medical facilities and personnel may be withdrawn if it is proven that they are being used for military purposes that harm the opposing party or deviate from their humanitarian function. However, such withdrawal is only valid if certain conditions are met, such as the existence of concrete evidence and the issuance of prior warning with a reasonable deadline. In the context of the conflict in Gaza, Israel has repeatedly stated that hospitals, including al-Shifa Hospital and the Indonesian Hospital, have been used by Hamas as command centers and rocket launch sites (al-Shareef, 2023). However, international organizations such as Human Rights Watch (HRW) and Amnesty International have concluded that there is no credible evidence to support those claims (Amnesty International, 2023). Sarbini Abdul Murad, Chair of the Presidium of the Medical Emergency Rescue Committee (MER-C) and coordinator of the Indonesian Hospital Development Project, also denied allegations that the Indonesian Hospital was being used as a military headquarters by Hamas (Wardah, 2023). In fact, some of the information provided by the Israeli military has raised doubts because it has not been independently verified. Therefore, in accordance with Article 52(3) of Additional Protocol I to the 1977 Geneva Conventions, civilian objects must not be targeted and must continue to be treated as civilian objects if their status is unclear.

Attacks on healthcare facilities, including the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza, objectively constitute war crimes and may also constitute crimes against humanity as defined in the 2023 Criminal Code. The fact that the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza has been repeatedly targeted indicates a widespread and systematic pattern of attacks against the civilian population and vital infrastructure. The following presents a timeline of attacks on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza.

No.	Periode	Peristiwa	Dampak
	October 7, 2023	According to a report from the Medical Emergency Rescue Committee (MER-C), the Indonesian Hospital was targeted in an	Some of the disadvantages include: One local MER-C staff member has died; 1 MER-C operational vehicle was destroyed; and

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		attack and set on fire (Hakim, 2026).	Wisma Rakyat Indonesia has sustained damage.
	November 20, 2023	According to a report by BBC News Indonesia, Israel launched an attack using artillery and missiles that struck the Indonesian Hospital (BBC News, 2023).	Killing at least 12 people and forcing the evacuation of 200 patients to Nasser Hospital in Khan Younis, in southern Gaza.
	May 19, 2025	According to a report from JPNN.com, Israel carried out a bombing raid near the Indonesian Hospital (JPNN.com, 2025).	The hospital was severely shaken; some medical equipment was even buried under the rubble, and services in the ICU, emergency room, and operating rooms were disrupted.
	June 2, 2025	According to a report from the Medical Emergency Rescue Committee (MER-C), the Indonesian Hospital was forcibly evacuated by the Israeli occupiers (MER-C, 2025).	MER-C has not yet been able to return to the Indonesian Hospital and continues to advocate and negotiate with various parties in order to reactivate the Indonesian Hospital through the “Rebuild the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza” program.
	April, 2026	According to a report by Kompas.com, Israeli forces occupied the hospital and turned it into a military headquarters/post, and put up “Rising Lion” propaganda banners (Pristiandaru, 2026).	This is considered a violation of international humanitarian law and an affront to the solidarity of the Indonesian people. The use of military symbols and propaganda atop the ruins of a destroyed hospital, especially when linked to a specific military operation, is a highly provocative and unjustifiable act.

The following is the text of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code:

“Any person who commits any of the following acts as part of a widespread or systematic attack, knowing that the attack is directed against the civilian population, shall be punished for crimes against humanity:

- a) murder, extermination, expulsion, or forcible displacement of a population; deprivation of liberty or other deprivation of physical freedom in violation of fundamental rules of international law; or the crime of apartheid, punishable by death, life imprisonment, or imprisonment for a term of not less than 5 (five) years and not more than 20 (twenty) years;
- b) slavery, torture, or other inhumane acts of a similar nature intended to cause severe suffering or serious injury to the body or to physical and mental health, punishable by imprisonment for a term of not less than 5 (five) years and not more than 15 (fifteen) years;
- c) persecution of a group or association on the basis of politics, race, nationality, ethnicity, culture, religion, belief, gender, or persecution on other discriminatory grounds that are universally recognized as prohibited under international law, punishable by imprisonment for a minimum of 5 (five) years and a maximum of 15 (fifteen) years; or
- d) rape, sexual slavery, forced prostitution, forced pregnancy, forced castration or sterilization, or other forms of sexual violence of equivalent severity, or the forcible abduction of a person, punishable by imprisonment for a term of not less than 5 (five) years and not more than 20 (twenty) years.”

Under the 2023 Criminal Code, Article 599 on crimes against humanity may be applied to the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza. This can be explained as follows:

- a) This provision requires a widespread or systematic attack against the civilian population. Several incidents of Israeli attacks on the Indonesian Hospital, occurring from October 7, 2023, through April 2026, demonstrate a widespread nature of the attacks. This is evidenced by the methods and weapons used in the attacks, which began with arson, progressed to artillery fire, and subsequently involved the use of missiles and bombs that destroyed medical equipment and disrupted the operations of the Indonesian Hospital. The culmination of these actions was the forced evacuation and seizure of the hospital to serve as a military base. Furthermore, these Israeli attacks meet the criteria for systematic attacks, as the sequence from the first to the last attack was sequential and planned with the aim of taking control of the Indonesian Hospital. The repeated attacks that crippled access to the Indonesian Hospital’s healthcare services for Gaza’s civilian population can be classified as part of a systematic attack against the civilian population.
- b) This provision requires the commission of specific acts as listed in subparagraphs (a) through (d). Attacks carried out by Israel against the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza from October 7, 2023, to April 2026, have caused several negative impacts, including the loss of life, the forced transfer of patients to Nasser Hospital in southern Gaza, the destruction of medical facilities, forced

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evacuation, and the conversion of the hospital into a military post. From these negative impacts, it can be seen that the attacks carried out by Israel have met the provisions of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code, letter (a).

Thus, the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza can be viewed as a concrete manifestation of a violation of international humanitarian law that aligns with the provisions of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code. Consequently, the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza may be prosecuted under Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code.

B. Indonesia’s Role in Utilizing the Universal Principles Guaranteed in Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code to Seek Legal Accountability for Israel’s Attack on an Indonesian Hospital in Gaza

Indonesia, as a country that condemns attacks on healthcare facilities in Gaza, including the Indonesian Hospital built with funds from the Indonesian public, has the authority to invoke the principle of universality as set forth in Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code. These principles allow Indonesia to prosecute serious human rights crimes and other international crimes, even if they occur outside its jurisdiction, provided that such crimes are listed in the Criminal Code and are of an international nature. The following table presents the provisions of Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code.

Article	Text of the Article
Section 6	The criminal provisions of this Act apply to any person outside the territory of the Republic of Indonesia who commits a criminal offense under international law that has been designated as a criminal offense in this Act.
Section 7	The criminal provisions of this Act apply to any person who commits a criminal offense outside the territory of the Republic of Indonesia, where the prosecution is assumed by the Government of Indonesia pursuant to an international agreement that grants the Government of Indonesia the authority to conduct criminal prosecutions.

The principle of universal jurisdiction is a principle in international criminal law that grants a state the authority to prosecute and punish perpetrators of certain crimes, even if the criminal act occurred outside its territorial jurisdiction and neither the perpetrator nor the victim is a national of that state (Ramdani, 2025). In relation to Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code, this principle can be applied to serious crimes against human rights, terrorism, corruption, money laundering, and narcotics, which are grouped into a separate chapter titled “Chapter on Special Crimes.” The grouping into a separate chapter is based on the characteristics (2023 Indonesian Criminal Code):

- a) The impact on the victims is widespread;
- b) Often organized on a transnational scale;
- c) The provisions governing criminal proceedings are specific;
- d) Often deviates from the general principles of substantive criminal law;
- e) The existence of law enforcement support agencies with specific functions and authority (for example, the Corruption Eradication Commission, the National Narcotics Agency, and the National Human Rights Commission);
- f) Supported by various international conventions, both those that have been ratified and those that have not yet been ratified;
- g) It is an act considered extremely wicked and reprehensible and is strongly condemned by society.

This is because the 2023 Criminal Code adopts international conventions, both those that have been ratified and those that have not, including Law No. 5 of 1998 on the Ratification of the Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment. Therefore, Indonesia has a legal basis to prosecute perpetrators of international crimes without being bound by factors such as nationality or the location where the act occurred (2023 Indonesian Criminal Code).

Article 6 outlines the scope of the subjects, territory, and types of criminal offenses to which this provision applies. The phrase “any person” confirms that this rule applies to all individuals, whether Indonesian citizens or foreign nationals. Meanwhile, the phrase “located outside the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia” indicates that Indonesian criminal law can still hold perpetrators accountable even if the acts were committed in another country. The criminal offenses in question are international crimes that have been incorporated into the national legal system; thus, the application of this principle is not automatic but depends on the existence of provisions in domestic legislation (Ramdani, 2025).

Article 7 governs Indonesia’s jurisdiction over criminal offenses committed outside the country’s territory, subject to specific conditions. Unlike Article 6, which applies directly to certain international crimes, this Article stipulates that prosecution may only be pursued if there is a basis in an international agreement. In other words, Indonesia requires legal legitimacy through bilateral or multilateral agreements that grant the state the authority to prosecute perpetrators (Ramdani, 2025).

This article uses the phrase “any person,” meaning that its provisions apply to all individuals, both Indonesian citizens and foreigners, provided the criminal act was committed outside Indonesian territory. However, because its application depends on the existence of an international agreement, the Indonesian government lacks the authority to prosecute unilaterally without a legal basis in the form of a valid agreement. Consequently, the scope of Article 7 is more limited than that of Article 6 (Ramdani, 2025).

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Attacks on Indonesian hospitals in Gaza, when examined in light of Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code regarding Crimes Against Humanity, can be linked to the principle of universality as stipulated in Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code. This is because Article 6 requires the application of the principle of universality to crimes recognized by international law and adopted into national law. Therefore, regarding crimes against humanity as defined in Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code, the Indonesian government has a basis for applying the principle of universality as set forth in Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code. Thus, the principle of universality in the 2023 Criminal Code can serve as an important tool for Indonesia to uphold the integrity of the law and international justice, while also strengthening Indonesia's role as a country that consistently upholds human rights and international humanitarian law.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, the following conclusions can be drawn.

1. The Connection Between the Attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza and Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code

The attacks carried out by the Israeli military against the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza from October 7, 2023, through April 2026 reveal a widespread and systematic pattern. The "widespread" element is evidenced by the escalation in attack methods (ranging from arson, artillery, missiles, and bombs to forced evacuation). The "systematic" element is fulfilled because the series of attacks appear sequential, planned, and aimed at paralyzing and taking control of the Indonesian Hospital from civilians. The impact of these attacks has resulted in loss of life, the forced relocation of patients, damage to medical facilities, and the conversion of hospitals into military bases. These negative impacts concretely fulfill the elements of a crime against humanity as stipulated in Article 599(a) of the 2023 Indonesian Criminal Code.

2. Indonesia's Role Through the Principle of Universality (Articles 6 and 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code)

Indonesia has the legal authority to prosecute perpetrators of international crimes committed outside its territory through the application of the principle of universality guaranteed in Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code. This article grants Indonesian criminal law the authority to prosecute "any person" (whether an Indonesian citizen or a foreign national) who commits an international crime that has been incorporated into national law. Unlike Article 6, which can be directly applied to international crimes regulated under national law, Article 7 of the 2023 Criminal Code has a more limited scope because prosecution cannot be initiated unilaterally and must be based on the existence of an international agreement (bilateral or multilateral). Since the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza meets the elements of a Crime Against Humanity under Article 599 of the 2023 Criminal Code (which falls under the category of special crimes), the Indonesian government legally possesses a strong normative basis to apply the principle of universality under Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code to hold the perpetrators of the attack legally accountable.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

The Indonesian government is expected to prepare and train law enforcement officials so that they are ready to progressively implement Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code in cases of serious international human rights violations that offend the world's sense of humanity, such as the attack on the Indonesian Hospital in Gaza.

It is hoped that the Medical Emergency Rescue Committee (MER-C) will continue to consistently advocate, negotiate, and document in detail and independently the chronology of events, the impact of the attacks, and physical evidence on the ground. Valid documentation is crucial for refuting one-sided claims by foreign military forces and will serve as primary evidence should legal proceedings be initiated in the future.

Legal scholars and researchers are encouraged to conduct more in-depth research on the enforcement mechanisms and specific procedural criminal law provisions necessary to apply the principle of universality in Indonesian courts. This is because the application of Article 599 through Article 6 of the 2023 Criminal Code requires procedural legal frameworks that extend beyond the borders of other sovereign states.

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